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Key Messages

- To enable an optimized selection of DC-link capacitors, fast and precise models of the single capacitors, including all kinds of derating, must be taken into account.
- The feasibility of capacitor optimization highly depends on the availability of detailed data, including frequency-dependent ESR, as well as temperature dependencies and aging effects.
- Even when such data are available there can be a significant difference to the physically built capacitors. Additional measurements must be taken.

Target Description

Mapping the capacitors from the design space by considering the application specification into the performance space.

Film Capacitor Selection

Film capacitor selection workflow.

Pareto plane demonstrating the impact of different capacitor series.

Exemplary ripple-current specification.

V_{DC}	730 V	Δv_{ripple}	1 V
γ	10 %	ϑ_{amb}	40 °C
T_{life}	30 000 h	i_{ripple}	Fig.
f	200 kHz		

Exemplary film capacitor specification.

Pareto plane demonstrating the impact of different ambient temperature.

Electrolytic Capacitor Selection

Electrolytic capacitor selection workflow.

V_{DC}	350 V	Δv_{ripple}	1 V
γ	10 %	ϑ_{amb}	60 °C
T_{life}	30 000 h	i_{ripple}	Fig.
f	20 kHz		

Exemplary electrolytic capacitor specification.

Electrolytic Capacitor Selection

Pareto plane demonstrating the impact of different capacitor series.

Pareto plane demonstrating the impact of parallel balancing/discharging resistors.

Capacitor Technology Comparison

Pareto plane demonstrating the impact of different capacitor technologies. Gray points show higher number of parallel capacitors than required.

Pareto plane demonstrating the capacitor cost.

V_{DC}	350 V	Δv_{ripple}	1 V
γ	10 %	ϑ_{amb}	60 °C
T_{life}	30 000 h	i_{ripple}	Fig.
f	2 kHz		

Exemplary capacitor specification for the technology comparison.

Validation and Measurements

Compensated measurement circuit for loss estimation.

Compensated measurement lab setup.

Calorimetric measuring chamber.

$C_{DUT,1} = B32714P0105K000 @ f_{res,meas} = 138 \text{ kHz (FILM)}$
 $C_{DUT,2} = B32714P6255K000 @ f_{res,meas} = 86 \text{ kHz (FILM)}$

Capacitor	Data source	$P_{C,loss,calc}$	$P_{C,loss,meas}$	Deviation
$C_{DUT,1}$	Datasheet	339 mW	205 mW	65 %
	Imp. Meas.	178 mW		-13 %
$C_{DUT,2}$	Datasheet	264 mW	208 mW	27 %
	Imp. Meas.	189 mW		-9 %

Compensated measurement results for film capacitors.

$C_{DUT,3} = MAL205736221E3 @ f_{res,meas} = 100 \text{ Hz (ELECTROLYTIC)}$

Capacitor	Data source	$P_{C,loss,calc}$	$P_{C,loss,meas}$	Deviation
$C_{DUT,3}$	Datasheet	22.8 W	8.2 W	179 %
	Imp. Meas.	8.5 W		3 %

Calorimetric measuring chamber results for electrolytic capacitors at 30 °C ambient temperature.

Open-Source Toolbox

Power Electronics Capacitor Selection Toolbox
 - Public Python toolbox
 - Free and open-source software
 - Community project
 - https://github.com/upb-lea/capacitor_selection_toolbox